

THE EPIC OF KHORAZM AND PEDAGOGICAL FUNDAMENTALS OF THE WORKS PERFORMED IN IT

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Abstract: This thesis discusses the technologies of artistic and ideological education of students through the Khorezm epic.

Key words: Educational system, Khorezm epic, technology, methodology, audio and video recording, rhythmic movement.

Introduction:

In the process of music education, by analyzing the pedagogical foundations of the performance of Khorezm epics, it serves as a tool for the development of epic traditions in the past and today, and for the young generation to have a high level of spirituality. Epic epic formulas appear in each genre in its own way. In particular, the epic formula is manifested in a unique way in romantic adventure, that is, in romantic epics. It is known that Romanesque epics are examples of classical epics. According to the researchers, the classical epic reflects the ideals of a single nation or nation. Motives specific to epic plots appear in folk epics, community interests and legal norms, the sense of justice in the ideal of the people are glorified, geneological, biographical, geographical and historical series are created in the epic, and finally, stable universal formulas in image and expression are widespread. is used.

From the above-mentioned features of the epic, it is known that systematicity in the performance of the epic is one of the necessary signs for the highest stage of the development of the folk epic. So, epic systematicity is not just a formal characteristic, but also a unique means of poetic perception of the reality typical of folk epics and its description, and expression of the spiritual world of the epic hero. Therefore, the poetics of stable epic formulas in Romanic epics is a scientific issue that requires special research

Now it is not a secret to anyone that Khorezm epic performance went through the stages of formation and live performance for a long time, and strong epic traditions were formed during these stages. And epic traditions are not abstract concepts, they consist of specific poetic events that operate on several levels. One of these traditions is the epic content, which includes the events of the work and the activities of the characters. Although epic content has a conditional connection with real life content, it is never equal to real life content.

As much as real-life content is variable and active, epic content is stable and traditional in nature.

Therefore, the epic content cannot be directly connected with the real-life content, the connection between them is realized through the stability of the epic tradition. This is the first level of relationship between epic reality and real reality.

Young people who are educated in the music culture classes of general secondary schools are especially protected from foreign ideas of the modern world, and at the same time, the epic genre, which reflects the content of the traditions and values of the people, which is formed in the course of a long life, has an educational significance in it. should study deeply and deeply.

The second feature of epics is the methods and means of expressing the content of the work in stable poetic forms. It is at this level that epic formulas, their historical roots, their expressed content and their artistic functions are highlighted. First of all, it should be said that the performers of epics, i.e. bakhshis, try to attract the attention of young and old listeners to the scenes of the work being performed.

Because the creators of the Khorezm epic created epic formulas based on life conclusions of distant ancestors about events in nature and society, tested, confirmed or denied in their life experiences. The permanence and immutability of such conclusions paved the way for the formation of a rare blessing called memory in the story of the students or listeners. In simpler words, listening to epics and learning them are pillars that keep memory strong for general secondary education students. The epics of Khorezm (Goroqli, Ashiq Gharib and Shokhsanam) are related to a specific plot, but they hold the epic mind and epic memory of the people, encourage and guide them to be badiha. In this sense, the important, leading methodological feature of folk epics is important as they have educational significance.

It is important to determine the content of stable epic formulas, their level of traditionality, and the tasks performed by each formula in the text of the epic in order to deeply and correctly understand the pedagogical essence preserved in folk epics. Uzbek pedagogues have made a number of observations about the artistic specific pedagogical tasks of revealing the good and bad qualities of folk heroes, and the historical basis of the content expressed in some epics¹. They expressed significant opinions about didactic events related to specific situations in the plot of the epic and not related to the plot.

The representatives of Khorezm epic performance school and their

successors are active in this regard until now, as advocates of great works, in order to preserve this rare and valuable heritage, in order to preserve their scientific didactic educational significance. Pedagogical views in the epics of Khorezm, that is, educational and educational aspects, are as follows:

- Instill love, loyalty, and protection of the motherland among middle school students of the general secondary education school.
- Parents, brothers and sisters take responsibility for the family as a whole, as well as protect the elderly.
- To develop qualities such as loyalty, kindness, hatred of evil and gratitude for good.
- To preserve concepts such as monotony and faithfulness to a real husband, as well as proper actions and correct assessment of the situation, etc.

Great attention to Khorezm epics started mainly from the end of the 19th century, during the Khiva Khanate, and special attention was paid to its development. The above-mentioned aspects of the epics of Khorezm, especially the epic "Goroqli" and its variants, contain events embodying the pedagogical point of view presented in different situations and in different forms. What is valuable for us is that each of the heroes of the epic from which we can make good conclusions is important to get their words and pedagogical conclusions accordingly. However, it should be noted that epics are an invaluable source of education for the Uzbek people.

So, stable epic formulas are not related to a specific plot, but are based on the epic consciousness, knowledge and epic memory of the people, guide them in the process of performance of folk epics, and consist of poetic patterns that allow creation. A person lives with a sense of hope for the future. If his lights of hope are not lit, his fate will be dark and his life will pass in vain. The arrival of spring, the opening of flowers, the drunken singing of nightingales, the epic hero's hope for life, the possibility that spring will come in his life, and that his life will be filled with pleasure, give the epic image its own charm.

So, it serves to reveal the pedagogical content of the work, which is concentrated in content, to prepare the listener mentally to inform about the situation of the hero of the epic in a difficult situation. However, it is explained symbolically by means of artistic movements expressed in the work. Due to the fact that Khorezm's epics have a complex of traditional contents related to pedagogy with educational significance, they help the students to understand the realities

correctly and each of them serves to achieve moral perfection in a specific content. 'liq form is understood.

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